

E-learning as an Introduction to Developing Education for Children with Special Needs in the Sultanate of Oman (Case study of Dhofar Governorate)

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Abstract

The study is intended to examine the use of e-learning in the education of children with special needs. It focuses on the potential of this type of learning to enhance the students' learning process. The researcher used the descriptive approach as it fits the purpose of this research. The study sample consisted of 50 teachers instructing children with special needs in the Dhofar Governorate. The researcher used the questionnaire as a study tool to measure the use of e-learning in teaching children with special needs. Among the study's findings is that e-learning increases the motivation of children with special needs and supports lesson preparation.

Introduction

Background of the study

The world today is undergoing a series of technological advancements. We are living in the age of information and communication technology which has transformed all areas of life, including education.

It seems that presently we find ourselves at the brink of another revolution, the so-called 'third wave.' It is a combination of technological progress and information wealth that has infiltrated society and reshaped public life, whether welcomed or not. Every new technology comes with higher capacity and performance, and a new set of applications and uses.

This unprecedented wealth of accessible knowledge and information has increased the rate and scope of scientific research tools, which also has had a tangible impact on education and teaching and learning processes. Special education is concerned with the teaching and learning of children with special needs, who either suffer from a chronic disability or illness that affects their physical, sensory, mental, or social ability. Special needs is the term used to describe disabilities that prevent learners from taking full advantage of the educational and professional experiences that are afforded to other persons. Thus, disability stands between them and other members of society in terms of equal competition and access. Therefore, those individuals require specially designed educational programs and training opportunities to develop their abilities, so that they can live and integrate with society, which is natural right (Ebaid, Magda El-Sayed, 2000, p. 19).

Special education pays specific attention to learners with special needs through adapting the curricula and teaching methods to align with their needs, which allows them to be integrated with their peers and attend in regular classes. It also means providing intensive support to special education teachers and general education teachers, which helps them to implement adequate strategies. The current decade has witnessed a tremendous development in the area of disability and learning. Various countries have been active in developing programs in the field of disability. The response to the issue of disability has to be comprehensive; it remains ineffective if it does not pay attention to all aspects of the problem. More importance has to be given to disability prevention programs, since they represent an early measure that significantly reduces the incidence of disability and shortens many moral and material efforts required for care and rehabilitation (Abdel Razik, Salah Abdel Samie, 2020).

In this regard, the Children of Disability Association states that special education teachers must have the skills to use education technology, and also the ability to create a purposeful learning environment. This concerns building positive attitudes towards the use of educational technology for individuals with special needs. Teachers can help students to use various modes of communication which contribute to the integration of that group into the external community (Zaghloul et al., 2017)

To achieve the main goal of the study the key terms are defined as follows:

E-learning: It is the delivery of information through electronic media including the internet, intranet, extranet, satellites and laser discs, in addition to direct education and computer education. This study includes aspects of distance education.

Persons with special needs: In the context of this study they are children with simple, medium, and acute medical conditions. Children with special needs in integration schools in the UAE include the hearing impaired, visually impaired, blind, those with organic (physical) disabilities, speech disorders, and the deaf (Waqfi, 2009).

Study Problem

The increased attention to persons with special needs is due to the increasing number of disability cases worldwide. The 2016 global statistics on disability indicate that approx. one billion people or 15% of the global population suffer from some form of disability. Disability is more prevalent in developing countries. One-fifth of the total population or between 110 and 190 million people are severely disabled.

The economic, legislative, physical, and social environment in a country may create or facilitate barriers to the participation of persons with disability. Those barriers include inaccessible buildings, lack of transportation, difficult access to information and communications, inadequate level of services and funding, lack of data, and the paucity of efficient and effective evidence-based policy analysis (World Health Organization, 2011).

Educators have proposed suitable and effective methods and means to create an interactive environment that attracts the interest of learners with special needs and urged them to share their views and experiences. E-learning is one of the most successful means to create this rich learning environment, and students are given the opportunity (and responsibility) to search for information and formulate it which also helps develop their thinking skills.

E-learning is one of the most important features of future school education. The current age is characterized by scientific and technological progress, which makes it necessary for education to keep up with these changes and make use of this wealth of information and data. A timely response is needed due to the increase of students, shortage of teachers, and long distance.

The present changes have led to the emergence of new patterns and ways in education, especially in the field of special needs education: learners with special needs can now adjust their learning to their energy and ability level, determine the pace, and incorporate their previous experiences and acquired skills. The new concepts of programmed education, computer education, and remote education allow learners to study from any location and without the need of permanently assigned teachers. This new emphasis is represented in the development of additional education programs and rehabilitation services that will hopefully improve the educational level of people with disabilities, thereby increasing their higher education and career opportunities.

Teaching people with special needs requires adapting the current teaching methods through modifying them and offering more flexible classroom practices corrective activities that focus on strengths, and the use of the capabilities available to them. This also includes modifications in teaching methods, modifying the learning environment, curricula, teaching techniques, and evaluation modes, and the (Mohammed, Adel Abdullah, 2012, p. 365).

The concept of e-learning as one of the methods delivering learning content relies on modern computer technology, the world wide web, and other digital and online media (CD-ROM, educational software, e-mail, chat rooms, and virtual classes). Extensive changes have happened in education, and the labor market—in constant need of new skills and qualifications—constantly imposes new rules and develops new specializations that meet the needs of the new economy. Thus, curriculum need to be reviewed to keep pace with these developments.

Especially the Arab world is in need of a quantitative and qualitative shift in school education. This is not limited to Oman and applies to all Arab countries. This region has to develop new educational mechanisms that support and complement traditional education. For instance, electronic education has the potential to improve, support, and build a capable and forward-looking new generation. This challenge needs to be met as soon as possible. The education process is a complex process; it involves preparing all young learners, those with disabilities and those without, for their full integration into society (Mubarak, 2005; 2017). All students have the right to access technology in their learning. This is a fact that needs to be established in Omani society, especially since the introduction of education technology will enable students with special needs to receive the same quality of education that their peers.

From this perspective is taken the idea of this research to clarify the role of e-learning in special needs education, with focus on its application in Dhofar, Oman. The aim of this study is to increase public awareness of the rights of persons with special needs, and the importance of their access to equal education opportunities consistent with their abilities and aptitudes; therefore, this research tries to answer the following questions:

What is the role of e-learning in the development of special needs education in Dhofar, Oman?

1. How is e-learning used in the education of people with special needs?
2. How can e-learning be used to develop special needs education?

Study hypotheses:

1. There is a statistical indicative of a positive impact of e-learning in students with special needs from the perspective of the sample.
2. There is a statistical indicative of a positive impact of e-learning in students with special needs due to gender.

The current study aims to recognize the concept of e-learning and its importance for special needs categories, and to present some of its applications. The significance of the current research lies in the importance of those special needs categories in the context of e-learning. This is determined by the following two aspects of importance:

Theoretical: The theoretical importance of the study lies in the following points: 1) the growing role of e-learning and its contribution to educational aims; 2) necessity to introduce teacher-student learning as part of the teaching and learning process; 3) to devise a mechanism to activate e-learning; 4) to establish methods of development for students with special needs.

Practical: The practical importance of the current study lies in the following points: 1) to generate outcomes that benefit those who improve and develop the educational process for students with special needs; 2) to prepare highly skilled and experienced teachers who can fulfil their specific role; 3) to assist those involved in developing special needs curriculums; 4) to assist those involved in the special needs integration in the schools (planning and organization); and 5), to help school communities in the development of skills included in e-learning.

This study is meant for the benefit of all stakeholders: the special education teachers under the Ministry of Education in Oman, the officials responsible for planning the education of persons with special needs, managers of public and private special educational institutions, decision-makers, and researchers in the field of education in general and special education in particular.

The study's limitations are determined by the topic and are reflected in the title. Thus, the discussion is limited to e-learning and its importance in the development of education for persons with special needs. The study has certain spatial limits, as the application of the field study concerns only the integration of students with special needs (students with hearing disability, mental disability, or visual disability) in Dhofar. Due to the homogeneity of the 11 educational districts in Oman, the schools share the same demographic characteristics. Besides, there is a geographical diversity in the Governorate of Dhofar, ranging from the sea, the plain and the mountain (al-Khamesi, 2015, pp. 41-48). In addition, the special needs education system is unified in all integration classes distributed across the educational districts of Oman. This study is also limited by time, as the field study was applied in the first semester of the academic year 2017/2018.

Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

International efforts to protect children with special needs

The comprehensive International Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities of the United Nations, 2008, supports this development. Article 24 demands the recognition of the right of persons with disabilities to education—without exception—on the basis of equal opportunities. All member states have to ensure an inclusive educational scope at all levels of public education and lifelong learning (UN report: 2008). It builds on the important role that people with special needs of different groups can play in development, if they are well qualified. This is also in accordance with the principle of equal opportunity and in line with the growing efforts adopted by the Sultanate of Oman in promoting education and care for all categories of society. Whether ordinary students or students with disabilities, all students have been integrated into regular classes in public schools (Saeed al-Saeed, 1, 81:2006).

This integration is divided into two levels:

Partial integration: Students with special needs are taught in separate classes within regular schools, thus allowing them to participate with their ordinary peers in some activities.

Full integration: Students with special needs are taught in regular classes, and special services are provided under the supervision of specialists. This allows them to participate in all school activities.

In integrated schools, special education and education work together in a collaborative and complementary manner to create effective classroom environments for all students (Burden, 2013, 28). School integration is designed to support all students in the form of assistance support programs that are appropriate to their individual needs. The most important part of the process of integrating children with special needs in public schools is social integration, where they participate in various educational activities (e.g., physical education, art, music, break times, clubs, vacations, camps, and other activities).

Many studies have pointed out that children with special needs in integration classes, who are offered modified curricula and individual educational programs in language skills, show a better ability to express themselves. In addition, integration offers children with special needs appropriate opportunities to improve their self-concept and socially related behaviors.

However, integration may not be the best solution for all children with special needs; some may not be able to succeed in different integration situations because of their different needs and the ineffectiveness of the

services available to them. So the strategy of providing adequate school facilities in Oman, according to the school integration plan, is a long-term commitment of the Ministry of Education to build new schools, renovate existing schools and furnish them to ensure that they are compatible with the ambitious educational plans for integration, and educational development for all students. Furthermore, public education is expected to achieve the best international standards in an environment that fits the technological development in the 21st century and is in line with Oman's Vision 2040.

It is clear from the above that there is an increased and intended interest in people with special needs, whether at the level of the Abu Dhabi Education Council or at the level of the state in general. The shared aim is to organize educational development programs for students with special needs in terms of setting concrete and achievable goals, devise curriculums, adapt teaching methods, build up-to-date learning resource rooms equipped with the relevant technologies, and train teaching and learning specialists. These goals can only be achieved through professional organization, administration, supervision and other components of the educational process (Ministry of Education, 2011).

Role of e-learning in the education of children with special needs

From the aforementioned we can summarize the role of e-learning in the education of people with special needs in line with the role of modern technology in setting future visions, services, and special educational programs, and innovative creative solutions to the problems of education. This contributes to the reformulation and design of the educational content in a way that helps students with special needs to access information easily. It also supports the application, practice, training, and actual testing through diverse educational practices to form their character and train them in effective communication (social skills), in addition to providing educational services that activate their mental abilities and protect them from psychological problems. The ultimate goal is to see these students successfully integrated into society as productive and self-reliant members, and not dependent on their family (al-Bataa, 2010).

The role of education technology in providing solutions for students with special needs can be divided as below.

Physical solutions: The provision or acquisition of hardware, materials, means, educational resources, and software.

Intellectual solutions: They are derived from teaching and learning theories and converted into educational competencies to establish an appropriate educational environment. Education specialists are trained according to educational standards and attain their qualification through preparation programs.

Design solutions: They include certain technical methods to designing and develop learning resources and educational programs and materials suited to the category of learners and their needs.

Ahmad (2015) proposed the use of assistive technology to support learning designed for all students in the comprehensive classroom environment instead of special rooms for learners with special needs. This was to equalize the approach of learning for the disabled on the basis of equality with their peers, which means that the teaching strategies, teaching design, and all auxiliary tools and devices meet the needs for all learners. The study recommended that students with special needs should be integrated into the public learning environment, while providing the necessary support and assistance to give them more space to present their capabilities.

Balmeo et al. (2014) aimed to determine the extent of integration of educational technologies in the classroom environment, and examine the problems that impede integration from the teachers' perspective. The tool was applied to a group of teachers in Baguio City, and the study concluded that the availability and use of educational technologies in the classroom was limited due to problems that prevented successful integration. The study recommended to integrate educational techniques into learning environments for people with special needs to develop their skills and to meet the challenges that limit their educational attainment and their ability to adapt to life in society.

Sider et al. (2014) aimed to support the educational needs of students in the comprehensive classroom environment through assistive technology in the city of Ontario, Canada. The result showed that assistive technology enhances the students' ability to do the assignments and to accomplish study tasks efficiently and independently. It recommended the school management and decision-makers to enhance the school teachers' ability so that they can effectively use assistive technology tools and devices with students of special education needs.

Al-Juhani et al. (2005) aims to identify the obstacles faced by teachers of students with learning difficulties, in particular the use of teaching aids to develop reading skills. The result showed that there are constraints in relation to the students' use of hearing aids at a moderate degree, and constraints in the use of visual teaching aids and technical devices at a high degree. Statistically significant differences were found in the average response of teachers towards the use of teaching aids with students with special needs, especially in regard to male teachers, and the absence of a statistically significant difference for any of the variables of qualification and experience.

Objective of field study

The aim of the study field is to recognize the role of e-learning in developing special needs education from the perspective of special education teachers in Dhofar, Oman.

Research Methodology

The current study uses descriptive methodology which entails the description and analysis of data, obstacles, and problems related to the current reality of the use of e-learning and its role in developing education for children with special needs in Oman. The researcher attributes the choice of the descriptive methodology to the fact that descriptive research facilitates the collection of accurate descriptions of the existing conditions. It also elicits the important relationships that are based on different phenomena and explains the meaning of the data, which provides the researchers with useful and valuable information. This helps to plan, revise, and set the right foundations for guidance and change, while also allowing us to “understand the present and its causes and chart future plans and trends.” (Duydraa, 2000, p. 184)

This study relied on conducting personal interviews for the study sample that are presented in questionnaire form. It was prepared through defining the questions in advance in a well-organized and coordinated manner, in addition to questioning the interviewees and discussing the main points of the research subject in order to obtain information, opinions, and behaviours that can be revealed as the result. The study tool represented in the questionnaire was applied to a sample of male and female teachers of special education (Basic Education Schools 5–9) in Dhofar, Oman. The number of teachers in the selected sample reached 50 teachers who answered the questions according to a three-degree Likert scale (‘yes’ (3); ‘to some extent’ (2); ‘no’ (1)).

Field study tool

The study tool was represented in the questionnaire directed to the study sample (prepared by the researcher) and designed according to the several consecutive steps, including:

1. Determine the quantity and quality of the data to be collected by carefully reviewing the study problem, its questions, and what the study seeks to obtain in terms of information and answers.
2. Determine the general structure of the questionnaire form so that the questions are arranged in the list in a stereotypical manner. They consist of a set of successive units, each of which includes a specific idea for which information is intended to be collected.
3. Prepare initial draft of questionnaire including cover page, data, title, and entity in charge.
4. Formulate easy, simple and clear questions; preparing a form confirming the confidentiality of the data and its use for research purposes only; requesting the cooperation of the sample members in giving the data.
5. Use phrases that are suitable for closed questions for which a set of alternative answers are offered to choose from.
6. Develop alternative answers that show the intensity of the response (Scaled Response scale); the potential answers range from support to rejection; this type of questions are used for ease of classification, classification, and analysis.
7. Present the initial form of the questionnaire to arbitrators (a list of the names of the arbitrators), where they tick (√) in front of one alternative according to the appropriateness of the phrase for the purpose for which it was set; a space is left after each axis to express an opinion on the amendment, omission, or addition of a new phrase not included in the questionnaire.
8. Confirm that the questionnaire includes 17 questions targeting the teachers of special education.

The study sample

The study sample depended on a random sample from male and female teachers of special education in Dhofar (Middle Schools 5–9) who answered the research questionnaire and participated in the interviews. The field study was applied, and the researcher used the intentional sampling method, which means selecting a sample whose elements are deliberately selected by the researcher due to the availability of some characteristics in these individuals rather than others. “This type of sample is used if the necessary data for research is available in one group of the community rather than others.” The researcher chose this type of sampling because it leads to “an increase in the accuracy of estimates and a decrease in the size of the error” (Badr, 1994, p. 330).

The number of the selected sample members reached about 60 forms, and the number of the correct forms used in the analysis was 50 forms. The study sample consisted of 50 male and female teachers of special education in Dhofar.

Table 1 Division of the sample of teachers

	Governorate	Number	Percentage %
	Original sample population in Dhofar	91	100
Total study sample		50	54

Table 1 refers to the original population; the selected sample was 20%

Table 2 Distribution of the study sample based on gender

	Gender	Number	Percentage %
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	Male	40	80
	Female	10	20
Total		50	100

The data in the above table indicates that the study sample of special education teachers consists of 40 male teachers at 80%, and 10 female teachers at 20%. This is due to the large number of male teachers in special education, mostly due to the prevailing customs and traditions that do not encourage women to work or even enter the public sphere.

Table 3 Division of the sample teachers according to specialization

	Specialization	Number	Percentage %
	Educational	35	70
	Non-educational	15	30
Total		50	100

This table indicates the study sample according to specialization consisting of 35 specialized educational teachers at 70% of the study sample, and 15 non-specialized educational teachers at 30%, due to teachers who are not special education graduates.

Table 4 Division of the sample teachers according to years of experience

	Specialization	Number	Percentage %
	Less than 5 years	25	50
	5–10 years	15	30
	More than 10 years	10	20
Total		50	100

This table indicates the sample of the study according to years of experience consisting of 25 teachers with less than five years at 50%, 15 teachers from five to ten years at 30%, and ten teachers of more than ten years at 20% of the study sample, due a large number of teachers who are fresh graduates.

Veracity of the study tool

The current study relied on calculating the veracity of the questionnaires by determining the arbitrators' honesty. Here, the researcher presented the questionnaires in their initial form to 15 expert arbitrators from academic teaching staff of Ain Shams University, Benha University and Al-Azhar University in Egypt, and Sultan Qaboos University in Oman. The arbitrators were asked to give their feedback on the questionnaire in terms of the suitability of the axes and phrases, the clarity of the wording and their linguistic integrity, and the omission, modification, and addition of phrases. Based on their recommendations, the questionnaire design was reformulated. The total percentage of approval of the questionnaire axes and phrases was between 90% and 100% after omitting inconsistent phrases.

To increase its veracity the questionnaire's consistency coefficient was calculated, followed by the subjective veracity coefficient:

$$\text{The veracity of the whole questionnaire} = \sqrt{0.84} = 0.92$$

This meant that the questionnaire subjective veracity coefficient reached a degree of more than 0.92 (high) indicating that the questionnaire has a high degree of veracity and is suitable for application to the study sample members. In order to ensure the stability of the questionnaire, it was measured by applying the tool to a scoping sample consisting of ten teachers before re-applying it after 20 days on the same group (without prior notice), in order to ensure the stability of the tool. This stability is measured statistically by the correlation coefficient between the raw scores obtained in both times; the questionnaire obtained a stability coefficient greater than (0.85), which indicates stability.

Statistical methods for data analysis

In the statistical treatment of the study tool (questionnaire), the researcher relied on SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences), an integrated computer package for data entry and analysis. Additionally, to the descriptive analytical approach was used to test the research hypotheses and achieve its objectives through collecting primary and secondary data. For data analysis the researcher used some statistical methods like Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient; the result indicated that the value of the stability coefficient Alpha is equal to more than 0.8 (strong) and confirmed the validity and correlation of the form.

Analysis and discussion of result

Based on the above-mentioned procedures that included defining the objectives of the field study, procedures for building study tools, arbitration, calculating the veracity and reliability coefficient of the study tools, selecting the study sample, and statistical methods used to process, certain results were produced which will be discussed below.

The results below answer to the first study question on the role of e-learning in developing the education of people with special needs, as perceived by the sample group members.

Table 5 Role of e-learning in developing the education of people with special needs in Dhofar, as perceived by the sample group members

Phrases	Yes		fairly		No		Arithmetic mean	Relative weight
	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %		
I am aware of the characteristics of children with special needs and their inclination for educational technology games.	29	58	15	30	6	12	2.46	0.820
I prepare entertaining programs and electronic games that bring joy and pleasure to children with special needs and relieve stress and anxiety.	17	34	15	30	18	36	1.98	.660
I use e-books/ recorded books.	30	60	11	22	9	18	2.42	0.807
I use simple methods and materials that help me increase interaction with children with special needs.	11	22	14	28	25	50	1.72	0.573
I help children with disabilities (deaf, hearing-impaired) to read and interpret projector images.	27	54	16	32	7	14	2.4	0.800
I help children with special needs to use modern technological innovations (headphones, amplifiers, sound reinforcements, etc.).	14	28	21	42	15	30	1.98	0.660
I prepare electronic programs for deaf and hearing-impaired children as a visual educational method that takes the theatre in form, and the curriculum in content.	10	20	15	30	25	50	1.7	0.567
I am interested in innovations and keep up with new advances in technology useful for people with special needs.	17	34	15	30	18	36	1.98	0.660
I train blind children on touch and oscilloscope computers.	13	26	21	42	16	32	1.94	0.647
I help provide assistive technology for special needs education.	10	20	14	28	26	52	1.68	0.560
I overcome class time by using assistive technology in teaching special needs.	12	24	10	20	28	56	1.68	0.560

There is no internet available in my classrooms and learning resource center for children with special needs	30	60	11	22	9	18	2.42	0.807
I participate in training courses for in-service teachers to use special techniques to help young learners with special needs.	16	32	14	28	20	40	1.92	0.640
I involve the school technician to operate special assistive devices for teaching students with different disabilities	10	20	15	30	25	50	1.7	0.567
I prepare classrooms technically to use special techniques with children with special needs in the learning process.	18	36	19	38	13	26	2.1	0.700
I assist in solving the problem of the lack of learning resource rooms that are equipped with technologies to help young learners with different disabilities.	22	44	16	32	12	24	2.2	0.733
I help overcome the lack of educational assistive technologies for children with special needs in the school.	14	28	15	30	21	42	1.86	0.620

As evidenced in the above table there is a high impact of e-learning in developing education for people with special needs in Dhofar, as perceived by the sample group. Less than 30% is interpreted as low level impact, above 50% as high-level impact, and between 30% and 50% as medium level impact. The study sample varied between 30% and 50%, which means that they ranged from medium to high level.

Findings of the study

First, there is an overall awareness of teachers that young learners have an inclination to play, as well as a frequent use of e-books for children with special needs, which enhances the chances of developing this type of education. The adequate training and preparation of special needs teachers contribute to this, and the teachers like to explore new technologies applicable in their field. This result is consistent with a study on good preparation practices for the classroom environment through the use of modern technology (Ahmad, 2015).

Second, several teachers cooperate with school administrators to enrich the learning experience of children with special needs. They do this by keeping pace with new advancements in education technologies that are suitable for special needs education and attend such training programs (Abdul Samie, 2020). However, the result also indicates a weakness in group thinking; the level of group responsibility of some teachers and school administrators towards improving the educational process needs to be further increased.

Table 6 Response levels of sample group members

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Low	15	30
Average	17	34
High	18	36
Total	50	100

The above table shows that all response levels range from 30% to 50% of the sample, meaning that there is also an increase in the impact of technology and e-learning on the learning process of children with special needs.

Suggestions of the study

Based on the results of the study, some of the following suggestions can be made to further the development of special needs education:

1. Provide the Ministry of Education with all information on e-learning means required for children with special needs.
2. Raise cultural and scientific awareness through conferences and seminars that deal with the use of e-learning means for children with special needs.
3. Acknowledge the needs of children with special needs when deciding on e-learning methods, and take into account the difficulty and level of learning for children with special needs.
4. Provide e-learning means in special learning resource center for children with special needs in all integration schools.
5. Prepare and design e-learning in preparing and design special programs for educating children with disabilities, each according to his disability.
6. Provide continuous technical support for teachers to appreciate the potential of assistive technologies in special needs education.
7. Provide training courses for teachers and family of learners with special needs to allow discussion and exchange of ideas and experiences.
8. Involve special education teachers in the preparation of special software for children with special needs.
9. Conduct field studies to identify the needs of children with special needs in light of technological advancements in education.

General conclusion of the study

There is an impact of e-learning in developing education for children with special needs in the Governorate of Dhofar from the point of view of the sample members through the percentages of response of the sample members.

Special needs teachers tend to be sufficiently aware of children's tendency to play. Furthermore, they frequently use e-books in the classroom and are aware of recent developments in technologies that can be used to support special needs education.

Also, the provision of training and preparation programs that are available to special needs teachers do indeed support the use of e-learning in classroom activities. Overall, there is good cooperation of special education teachers with the school management, which facilitates the integration of new technologies that suit the specific requirements of the learners with special needs.

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